

Comparative Analysis of ESG Factors in Large Investment Firms Versus Impact-Focused Firms

Abstract

As environmental concerns become increasingly urgent, investment firms play a growing role in shaping environmental and social outcomes. One prominent way this occurs is through green investing, a type of investing whose reliability relies on companies' self-reported environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors. The concept of green investing has been around for over twenty years, yet its ability to accurately measure an investment firms' commitment to the environment has been questioned. This paper examines how large investment firms, such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, incorporate ESG factors into investment decisions in comparison to smaller impact-focused firms, such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners. Through a comparative analysis of the impact of their respective investments, self-reported environmental consciousness and financial scope, this paper finds that ESG factors often serve as risk management tools rather than accurate measures of environmental commitment. These findings suggest that current ESG measures inadequately capture true impact, highlighting the need for a new system to accurately measure these elements in order to guide business and clients to make more informed decisions about who they trust with their investments.

Keywords: ESG Investing; Impact Investing; Sustainable Finance; Green Investing; Investment Management; Environmental, Social, and Governance; Financial Institutions; ESG Ratings

Introduction

This paper compares large investment firms, including Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, with smaller, specialized firms such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, focusing on how each incorporates environmental and social factors into investment decisions. While large firms incorporate ESG standards primarily as risk management strategies, smaller firms place impact goals at the core of their investment strategies. This paper examines company missions, structures, services, and financial impact to highlight key differences and assess the future of environmental investing. As climate change becomes a more pressing issue, understanding which companies prioritize environmental and social factors can influence investors seeking firms that align with their values, particularly as ESG considerations become more prominent in financial markets.

There are significant differences in how traditional large investment firms, including Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, and smaller specialized firms, such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, incorporate environmental and social factors into their investment strategies. While both large firms, such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, and smaller companies, such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, consider environmental and social factors, smaller companies place impact goals at the core of their missions and investments, whereas larger firms

tend to incorporate ESG standards primarily as components of risk management rather than as a central priority.

This paper examines the backgrounds, including missions, operating structures, and financial impact to highlight key differences between larger and smaller firms and thus assess the future of environmental investing. This paper argues that while larger firms benefit from larger scope and focus, smaller impact-focused firms are more effective at prioritizing environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors into their investment strategies, a distinction that will become increasingly important in the future. The following sections will examine the missions, services, operating structures, size, and financial impact of four firms to highlight the differences between large and small investing firms and assess the future of environmental investing.

Background

Larger investment firms, such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, typically have a global scope, broad client base, and offer a wide range of services. Morgan Stanley has forty-two international offices, and Blackstone has offices across twenty-seven cities worldwide. Blackstone is an alternative asset management firm specializing primarily in private equity and real estate. Morgan Stanley is a full-service global investment bank and wealth management firm. Both firms are publicly traded and possess the global reach to influence large-scale investment decisions. Their expansive global reach allows them to influence investments across many different sectors, some of which emphasize environmental and social initiatives, while others do not.

Morgan Stanley is a large global financial services firm that offers a wide range of services to individuals, institutions and governments to raise capital. Although based in the United States, the firm began expanding globally in the 1960s and went public in 1968 to fund its growth. Today, Morgan Stanley is a diversified firm offering numerous services with a large international presence across countries. The firm primarily offers investment banking, sales and trading, financial planning, investment advisory, and asset management services, with several specialized subcategories within each area. While financially diversified, Morgan Stanley integrates ESG factors primarily as components of risk management rather than a core strategic focus.

Blackstone is a global alternative asset manager with multiple investment strategies—including private equity, real estate, and credit—and manages over one trillion dollars in assets, allowing it to invest across sectors for long-term growth. The firm went public in 2007 and offers a large range of investment strategies, deploying capital across both public and private markets. They were founded in 1985, significantly later than Morgan Stanley, and had initially started off as a small mergers and acquisitions firm. Today, Blackstone operates in twenty-seven cities worldwide and reported 13.23 billion in revenue in 2024. While Blackstone invests in some sustainable initiatives ESG considerations are not the primary focus of its overall investment strategy.

Smaller investing firms, such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, operate on a significantly narrower scale and therefore emphasize a single primary objective: impact investing. These firms specialize in sustainable investing, operate independently from traditional banks, and focus on making investments that are both environmentally and socially responsible. Although Sonen Capital is slightly smaller in size, it is a certified B corporation, meaning it meets high standards of social and environmental performance. Veris Wealth Partners, which is larger and was founded earlier, is also a certified B Corporation and integrates both, financial objectives and social and environmental goals into its investment approach.

Sonen Capital is an impact-investment advisor with a mission to generate financial returns alongside measurable social and environmental impact. The firm is a privately owned company, founded in 2011, specializes exclusively in impact investing. Sonen Capital is also a certified B Corporation, meaning it meets rigorous standards for social and environmental performance and frequently partners with specialist funds to achieve its impact goals.

Veris Wealth Partners is an independent, majority women-led, investment advisory firm that applies impact investing strategies across public and private markets. Founded in 2007, the firm was established with a mission to use market-based strategies to achieve social and environmental change and has been a certified B corporation since 2011. Veris Wealth Partners employs a holistic investment approach, integrating financial objectives with social and environmental outcomes across both public and private markets.

Larger firms (Morgan Stanley and Blackstone) and smaller specialized firms (Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners) differ in core values, services offered, size, company structure, and the environmental and social impact they achieve. Due to their size and scale, both Morgan Stanley and Blackstone have the capacity to invest broadly; however, as publicly traded companies, they cannot base investment decisions solely on ESG considerations. Smaller firms, by contrast, have greater strategic flexibility. Because of their smaller size, limited workforce, and organizational structure, they are better able to tailor investments to individual client needs. Both Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners are also privately owned, giving them the control to focus on environmental and social factors when investing. Overall, ownership structure (publicly or privately owned) and firm size appear to be the most influential factors in determining the importance placed on environmental investing. This distinction is logical, as publicly traded companies are obligated to prioritize profitability, which does not always align with environmentally focused investments, particularly as firms grow larger and face increased pressure to generate returns. As a result of the core structural differences, private, smaller firms are more likely to lead the future of environmental and social investing, as they retain greater control over investment priorities than publicly accountable firms. will likely be the ones who lead in environmental and social investing in the future, because they can simply decide what they want for their own companies rather than investors.

Company Missions/Values

The stated missions and core values of both large and small firms, while sometimes understated, offer important insight into the priorities they choose to present to clients. Morgan Stanley and Blackstone's core values tend to emphasize their customer's values: putting clients first, making them the most profit. In contrast, Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners' explicitly center their missions on environmental and social impact while still addressing client financial objectives. Together, these mission statements signal the image that each firm wants to project to their customers and the values it prioritizes most strongly.

Morgan Stanley's general core values include "doing the right thing, putting clients first, leading with exceptional ideas, committing to diversity and inclusion, and giving back." Overall, these values are broad, addressing multiple aspects of finance while also acknowledging environmental considerations. However, in practice, Morgan Stanley appears more focused on financial returns than firms such as Sonen Capital or Veris Wealth Partners (Morgan Stanley 2026). One important factor to consider is that Morgan Stanley has experienced ethical breaches; for example, in 2018, there was an instance where an employee misused confidential information with a client in order to make a trade (Goldstein). Although Morgan Stanley was cooperative and there was no evidence that corporate management was aware of this incident, the firm paid \$249 million in fines to settle the investigations by the Department of Justice and Securities and Exchange Commission in January of 2024. These violations, even if isolated and not representative of the firm as a whole, suggest a disconnect between Morgan Stanley's stated values and its actions, ultimately undermining trust in large financial institutions.

Blackstone's core values include to relentlessly pursue excellence, never compromise integrity, outperform through innovation, deliver for their customers, work humbly and work together. Their core mission is to "deliver enhanced returns and capital preservation over the long term," reflecting their strong partnership culture and personalized approach to investors. Their publicized goal when serving clients is to act as owners and builders, not just investors, in order to create lasting, long-term success rather than short-term gains.

The core of both mission statements is to maximize profit for their clients. With these core values, it seems impossible to prioritize ESG goals as well, as the nature of green investing is to balance profit with environmentally conscious decisions (Aschoff). Another factor to consider is that Morgan Stanley and Blackstone are both publicly traded, meaning they must take their shareholders' advice and needs into their investments as well, which typically means the company has added pressure to primarily focus on producing greater profit. The position they are in does not allow the same flexibility to prioritize sustainable investments, as shown by the mission statements and actual investment choices.

The difference between the websites, and mission statements of smaller companies versus larger companies is immediately apparent. For Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, they promise profit and to tailor their approach to their clients, while Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners boast their impact on the environment through their investments.

Sonen Capital's mission statement is "to deliver our clients high performing impact investments" and their vision is "to be the trusted partner of choice for asset owners seeking

investment solutions that address the world's most pressing challenges" (Sonen Capital 25). Sonen Capital also claims that they value investments that perform across all asset classes and impact themes, client centricity, and working in a passionate environment. They also emphasize their real-world impact through different sectors, like green real estate, clean power, sustainable timber, land and water resources, and environmental infrastructure, highlighting some of their projects on their website.

Veris Wealth Partners' values are integrity, equity and justice, global sustainability, inclusion and belonging, community and connection and authenticity (Veris Wealth Partners 25). Their executive summary in their 2024 impact report highlights the significant impact that the firm has made in climate solutions and the environment: around twenty-four million megawatt hours of renewable energy generated, over 1 million affordable housing units created, over forty-two million acres of land managed sustainably and they've supported racial and gender equity through the companies or organizations led by women and people of color.

Overall, these mission statements suggest a clear trend: large institutions tend to prioritize making profits for their shareholders, often placing environmental impact as a secondary concern. In contrast, smaller firms are more likely to focus on investments that solve environmental and social problems as a central part of their mission.

Overview of Services Offered by Companies

The services offered also differ from smaller to larger companies, with smaller companies having much more focused and concise services, and large companies spanning more services offered.

Morgan Stanley and Blackstone both offer a wide range of services. Morgan Stanley offers services in all sectors, including brokerage and investment advisory services, fixed income securities, financial and wealth planning, annuity and insurance, banking and retirement plan services. Blackstone offers real estate income trust, mutual funds, business development companies, interval funds, exchange traded funds and LSE-listed funds. Based on the scope and structure of these offerings, it is evident that these firms focus primarily on profitability.

Both firms offer services in varying sectors, including real estate, insurance, financial planning and retirement, showcasing the result of their international development. However, because larger companies offer many services, their ESG focus may be diluted. Thus, their breadth of services can benefit the average consumer but also simultaneously take away from any environmental or social good that they could be doing.

The smaller firms focused on impact investing operate as full-service investment offices, acting as experts for clients who want to delegate their investment management. These firms build customized investment portfolios based on both financial needs and impact goals. Specifically, Sonen Capital offers impact investing for "foundations & endowments," "individuals & families," and "institutions and advisors," allowing them to tailor strategies for each type of client. Similarly, Veris Wealth Partners offers impact investing for families, foundations, and endowments, showing a comparable client-focused approach

Both smaller companies have a clear goal, yet offer their services to many different types of clients. These tailored portfolios allow them to better account for their client's needs, as well as maximize environmental and social impact. In contrast, larger companies often choose the investment with the highest return, but because these smaller companies use tailored portfolios, they have the flexibility to choose investments that are environmentally conscious.

Larger companies inherently have the money and resources to fund larger -scale investment projects in different sectors, while smaller companies often focus on helping the environment while still attracting as much business as they can. One thing to note is that none of the larger companies have any services specifically targeted to clients interested in green or environmentally and socially conscious investing, creating a need for companies like Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners in the market. While ESG services do exist at large firms, they aren't nearly as central to company values and strategies as they are at smaller, impact-focused companies.

Size of Company

Similar to their services offered and their mission statements, there is an apparent difference in both the scope and impact that each company has made through various channels.

Larger companies typically tend to generate significantly more in revenue than smaller, more-specialized companies. Morgan Stanley's revenue in 2024 was \$68.1 billion across wealth management, institutional securities, and investment management (Birch). Blackstone also earned significant revenue in 2024, totaling \$13.23 billion. In comparison, Sonen Capital's revenue the same year was \$5.1 million (Sonen Capital Case Study) and Veris Wealth Partners' revenue was around \$7.5 million, underscoring the more limited scale and niche focus of specialized firms.

The amount of employees across all four companies also varies significantly. Morgan Stanley employs approximately 80,000 employees, Blackstone employs approximately 5,000 employees, both of which classify them as large, global firms. In contrast, Sonen Capital employs between ten to fifty people and Veris Wealth Partners has approximately thirty to forty employees currently. Morgan Stanley's employees span over forty-two countries, and Blackstone's employees span across twenty-seven cities internationally. Both Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, however, are based in the United States, with Sonen Capital operating solely in San Francisco, California and Veris Wealth Partners headquartered in San Francisco, California, with key offices in New York City, Portsmouth, Denver and Philadelphia, making it slightly larger than Sonen Capital. From both the number of employees and geographic presence, it is clear that larger companies' benefits come from their scope and reach to different places throughout the world, while smaller companies focus on specialized and personalized service, causing them to operate in fewer locations and employ fewer people.

The size of the companies creates an impact on the clients and investments they make. For Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, each investment matters to them and they have the ability to provide their clients with specialized feedback for their goals and needs. Their smaller

size may inhibit them from having the client base that larger companies may have, but their impact on the world is evident. Larger companies, while aiming to do the best they can, simply cannot focus on every client the way Sonen Capital could. For example, a \$500,000 client for Morgan Stanley would fall into a more common category, making the differentiating factors focused on client relationships rather than the size of a client; even if the quality of service for all their \$500,000 clients is the same size, they could never be as specialized as smaller companies. At Sonen Capital or Veris Wealth Partners, a \$500,000 client would be of a significantly larger size than typical, resulting in a specialized plan. However, given the values of the smaller companies, this would not detract from their other clients, ensuring everyone gets the service they need in a sustainable way.

The differing size of Morgan Stanley and Blackstone compared to Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners impacts the effects that each company can have on the world. The larger companies can have a much bigger impact on the world because of their international reach and greater scale of investments, meaning the choices they make will have a larger impact than any choices smaller, more impact-focused companies may make. While there is measurable impact that smaller companies have made, without the funding and resources that larger companies have, it's more arduous to create impact that outweighs that of larger corporations.

Structure of Company

Structurally, Morgan Stanley has three main branches: institutional securities, investment management, and wealth management. Morgan Stanley investment operations are under a publicly held corporation (Morgan Stanley), with their shares traded on the New York Stock Exchange. Because of this trading, they are owned largely by institutional investors, mainly the Mitsubishi UFJ Financial Group, The Vanguard Group, and BlackRock.

Blackstone's main sectors are structured into private equity, hedge fund solutions, real estate, and credit and insurance. While Blackstone is private equity, they are publicly traded, with complex partnership units controlled by senior management, like their CEO, CFO, etc. This gives those same senior managing directors control over the company, because they hold partnership units with significant voting rights. Underneath those senior members, a Board of Directors oversees the company operations, investments, etc. They also have significant stakes held by The Vanguard Group and BlackRock, institutional leaders in the capital market. The result of these shareholders holding a significant stake in larger companies reduces some of the freedom that smaller companies have to make investments influenced by ESG factors. Morgan Stanley is a public company, making it harder for them to make any investments that aren't supported by their shareholders. Similarly, Blackstone is also a public company, but operates through private equity, meaning they have shareholders, but make investments like a private company. Thus, Blackstone may have more freedom to make investments influenced by ESG factors if the company deemed it appropriate.

Conversely, Sonen Capital primarily works on impact-focused investment solutions. Similarly, Veris Wealth Partners focuses its capital on impact themes such as climate solutions,

sustainable agriculture, community wealth building, while investing across a diverse set of asset classes. The reason Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners are allowed to be impact-focused is because they are privately owned (and in the case of Sonen Capital, majority employee-owned). This enables them to account for ESG factors in their long-term commitments and investments.

Morgan Stanley is a public company and its leadership consists of a board of directors and investors. Similarly, Blackstone is also publicly owned and controlled by a board of directors representing investor interests. In contrast, Sonen Capital is majority employee-owned and is a registered investment advisor. Sonen Capital is privately owned, with a board of directors of six people, with a management team, investment team, and client service and operations team underneath them. Veris Wealth Partners has an expansive board of directors, specializing in investments, advisory, marketing and client service, controlling the company. They are also privately owned.

This demonstrates how Morgan Stanley and Blackstone's structure emphasizes different types of investing, while Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners are more focused on impact investing. Morgan Stanley and Blackstone both have branches within their larger divisions that focus on environmental, social, and governance factors, but they're not a main focus. At Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, it's their entire marketing and brand, meaning they focus closely on these aspects.

Impact Made

Through investments, these companies differ in both size and how much they choose to invest toward the environment. Morgan Stanley, out of \$1.8 trillion, invested \$820 billion into sustainable solutions (aiming to reach \$1 trillion by 2030), \$12 billion in women- and minority-owned investment products, \$20 million toward education, and they set a \$15 billion plan in 2020 to increase investments in lower-income communities (Morgan Stanley 2026, Morgan Stanley Portfolio Holdings 2025). They also have set \$20 million to support underrepresented students, and \$30 million to scale startups and nonprofits focused on inclusion. Through investments alone, there is a large portion (currently about half) put towards sustainable solutions, with more expected to grow in the future.

Blackstone, out of \$1.2 trillion invested, has invested around \$100 billion toward climate solutions over a decade, 40 million towards a program for underrepresented students, \$700 million towards an education platform in India, \$13 billion toward a student housing portfolio, \$33 million to companies focused on financial inclusion services, and \$705 million towards India's federal bank to expand access to financial services and promote financial inclusion in the area. A similar trend to Morgan Stanley can be found here, however, a smaller portion of total investments is invested toward ESG factors.

Conversely, Sonen Capital invested \$400 million towards impact investment strategies, a significant amount relative to their total investments, as well as \$75 million in first sustainable assets funds. While there are no publicly available investments to underprivileged communities, Sonen Capital has co-authored a framework for principles on how investing can help change

systematic racial inequalities (Sonen Capital 2025). Veris Wealth Partners invested \$2 billion towards sustainable environmental impacts, and have made impact through client investments towards underprivileged communities. Both these companies put a large majority of their investments towards these factors.

For these numbers, Morgan Stanley's net income was \$4.61 billion (\$2.80 per share), their total revenue was \$182 billion and their return on equity was eighteen percent. Blackstone's distributable earnings were \$1.89 billion (\$1.52 per share) and their net income was \$624.9 million, dropping twenty percent, following their Q3 performance in 2025. Sonen Capital's annual revenue was \$5.1 million, and Veris Wealth Partners had less than \$2 billion in assets, with their revenue being \$6.5 million.

Within these investments, the companies that received them differed. Morgan Stanley's top investments were Microsoft Corporation, NVIDIA Corporation, Apple, Amazon and Alphabet Inc. Blackstone's top investments were Cheniere Energy Partners, FirstEnergy Corporation, Corebridge Financial, Viper Energy, EQT Corporation (an energy corporation). Sonen Capital invested in GoodSam, an emergency response app, and Bankingly, which provides technology to financial institutions that support low-income issues in Africa and Asia, and more. Veris Wealth Partners invested in Jopwell, which connects minorities to job opportunities, Trimble, agriculture technology company, EV Connect, a public electric vehicle charging station, and Xylem, a water technology solutions company.

Successful Stories/Testimonials

Morgan Stanley was the lead underwriter for Google's \$4.4 billion IPO in 2004, co-managed Apple's \$100 million IPO in 1980, and advised Sycamore Partners on the \$23.7 billion acquisition of Walgreens Boot Alliance. Morgan Stanley provides testimonials from clients, saying that they had "clear financial plans, tailored strategies that fit goals" and that they helped clients "feel more confident about [their] financial future thanks to [Morgan Stanley's] guidance." However, external sources say that, although they have personalized guidance, they deprioritize clients whose accounts fall below a certain asset threshold, resulting in account access issues and slow processes (Yelp). This ties back to before, where large companies can't focus on ESG factors or specialize client service nearly as well as smaller companies can. While their size can enable them to make more profit, the quality of each individual investment seems to be lower.

Blackstone helped with the acquisition of Hilton Hotels in 2007 for \$26 billion, leading to its continued global success and acquired Ancestry.com for \$4.7 billion, accelerating its growth. These investments show their priority of profit, even though Blackstone is a private equity company. Given the nature of the companies they acquired, the likelihood that they incorporate ESG factors into their investments is low.

Sonen Capital's investments in Lyme Forest Fund III protected over 117,000 acres of land, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and expanded renewable energy through targeted investments. They invested in approximately 1.5 million acres of sustainably managed land from

2016 to 2021, provided almost 7 million people with access to clean solar, hydro and wind power, and saved or conserved over 83.4 kilowatt-hours of energy from 2016 to 2021. Veris Wealth Partners guided clients away from investing in fossil fuels and toward investments in solar and wind power projects, green building and sustainable agriculture. Ormat Technologies reduced 2.2 million metric tons of CO2 emissions, reducing carbon intensity. They also helped HydroOne, providing indigenous people with an opportunity to invest in transmission lines. Again, because Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners are both privately owned and impact-focused, their investments are primarily focused on environmental factors. All their successful investments are tied to environmentally and socially aware factors, once again showcasing their priorities.

These examples show the importance of both the size and priorities of companies when investing. Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners have stated their focus on impact investing and their status as privately held companies, and their stories and testimonials align with these facts. Morgan Stanley and Blackstone are both companies that are publicly owned and are focused on making the most profitable investments. Their investments bring in a large amount of money, but are not ESG effective, and the testimonials for Morgan Stanley shows that they both prioritize clients in a higher tax bracket and *place less emphasis on environmental factors*.

Criticisms towards Companies

A few commonly expressed critiques towards companies like Morgan Stanley and Blackstone are their inaccuracies regarding ESG ratings. In fact, seventy percent of executives (across multiple industries and regions) have reported that they lack confidence in their own ESG reportings, causing them to be incomplete and often dated. Given that these are the most used factors to determine larger companies' potential, it should be essential for them to be as accurate as possible.

For smaller firms, like Sonen Capital or Veris Wealth Partners, it can be hard to verify their claims on green investing because of a lack of standardized reporting entirely. These companies can make claims, but without the ability to verify their real impact it can be difficult to believe them. They also have a much smaller influence than larger companies, simply because of their nature. Because of their smaller influence and niche focus, it can be both difficult to get clients, with investments that may be too concentrated. Greenwashing, which is the process of marketing a firm as more environmentally conscious than it actually is, can be shown in firms such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, which claim they are environmentally conscious but the majority of their investments aren't.

Youth Movements

I hypothesize that in the future the younger generation will be more dedicated to ESG values, and these smaller firms will gain popularity and resources as more people become committed to environmental issues.

Alongside investing decisions, there are other ways to show environmental dedication that have been especially prevalent alongside younger generations: a few primary ways being protests, clubs at universities dedicated to these specific topics, etc. For example, Fridays for Future is an international movement of school students who skip classes on Fridays to participate in protests that demand action from political leaders to prevent climate change and to encourage the fossil fuel industries to switch to environmentally conscious forms of energy.

Another example of youth movements is Georgia Tech's Association for Sustainable Investment, which hosts events and discussions with students and administrators to promote sustainable investment practices. NYU Stern's club, Stern Net Impact, has fostered a community of students dedicated to leveraging their business knowledge for social change. And even larger firms, like USB, use impact investment to find opportunities that make a difference and to get quantifiable proof of results.

Final Takeaways

The triple bottom line is a business concept that thinks firms should "commit to measuring their social and environmental impact, in addition to their financial performance, rather than solely focusing on generating profit" (Miller 20). The triple bottom consists of profit, people, and the planet, meaning firms should aim to generate returns for shareholders while also considering their social and environmental impact. As shown through this paper, large firms such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone, and small firms such as Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners use these factors to varying degrees in their investment strategies.

Generally, larger firms like Morgan Stanley and Blackstone are better for the average consumer in need of regular investing. They primarily prioritize profit and people, often placing environmental concerns last. This approach helps explain why the larger firms have significantly greater revenues and offer a wider range of services than companies like Sonen Capital or Veris Wealth Partners. For these reasons, an individual who wants to invest environmentally may be better off at smaller, specialized firms, but for bigger corporations seeking environmentally conscious advice, larger companies with more resources may be more advantageous.

Smaller, impact-focused firms factor in the planet first, closely followed by people and profit. Both Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners highlight their measurable social and environmental impact on their websites while also emphasizing alignment with client goals. The differentiation between these companies on this basis clearly shows what they truly value most.

However, while larger firms often claim to care about the planet, it's unclear how much large firms actually do for environmental, social and governance (ESG) initiatives while investing, due to the limited publicly available evidence of real-world impact. Smaller, specialized firms are more dedicated to factors, showing many examples on their websites and in their impact reports and thus are a better choice for customers dedicated to ESG factors. While ESG ratings today aren't always accurate and can be prone to misinterpretation and internal corruption, investors who prioritize environmental and social factors while looking to make

profit while investing may benefit from choosing smaller firms, like Sonen Capital and Veris Wealth Partners, who are certified B-corporations.

Conclusion

Environmental, social and governance factors will continue to play a role in the future of investment firms. However, to maximize the effectiveness of these standards, perhaps the criteria for them should be changed. ESG factors can be inaccurate and often fail to measure a firm's real-world impact. Instead, ESG often ends up measuring "the potential impact of the world on the company and its shareholders", with officials from the companies they evaluate even saying that they aren't reflective of their firms environmental and social awareness in investments (Pucker 2022).

In the future, there should be various differentiating factors between companies to evaluate their effectiveness environmentally and socially, factoring in criteria such as the firm's actual investments, breaches of client confidentiality (similar to the breach at Morgan Stanley), and how much the firm truly prioritizes each client individually. Companies like Veris Wealth Partners and Sonen Capital have proved themselves as impact-investing firms and deserve their ESG ratings, but companies such as Morgan Stanley and Blackstone still have much improvement to do on these fronts, starting at the actual core of their investments.

The need for new differentiating factors begin from the fact that real impact will always begin at the core of a firm's investments, and until that standard is met, ESG ratings will always be inaccurate. However, until these standards are changed, consumers should be more intuitive in their choice of investing, looking at factors like actual investments, core values and testimonials before choosing a firm to entrust with their investments. The final takeaway is that larger firms often incorporate ESG standards primarily as risk-management tools, while smaller firms place impact goals at the core of their business and investment strategies. The choice to prioritize investments for companies that embody ESG values belongs to the client.

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